

**APPLICATION FOR INITIATION OF INSOLVENCY PROCEEDINGS
AND PROCEDURAL ASPECTS OF ITS FORMALIZATION****Salimova Iroda Mamayusufovna**

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Abstract: In the article, on the basis of substantive and procedural legal norms the requirements for the form and content of the application for initiation of insolvency proceedings are analyzed. Specific procedural aspects of formalization an application for initiation of insolvency proceedings are indicated.

Keywords: insolvency, bankruptcy, debtor, creditor, authorized state body, economic court, application, insolvency proceedings, case, signs of insolvency, The procedure for initiating an insolvency case is regulated by the Economic Procedure Code[1] and the Law “On Insolvency” of the Republic of Uzbekistan[2].

According to the main concepts defined in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan “On Insolvency” insolvency is the inability of the debtor recognized by the court to fully satisfy the claims of creditors for monetary obligations and (or) fulfill their duties on taxes and fees.

Insolvency proceedings may be initiated by the court only if there are signs of insolvency. The signs of temporary and permanent insolvency are different: temporary insolvency – the inability of the debtor to satisfy the claims of creditors for monetary obligations and (or) to fulfill their obligations for taxes and fees as of the date of applying to the court, if the debtor has not fulfilled the relevant obligations within three months from the date of occurrence, and by the city-forming enterprise and enterprises equated to it – not fulfilled within six months;

permanent insolvency – if the debtor's obligations exceed the value of their assets on the date of filing an application with the court and in the reporting period at the beginning of the year in which the application was filed, and in the reporting period at the beginning of the previous year, if the application was filed by the debtor in the first quarter of the year.

An application for inability to pay can be submitted by the debtor, creditor and authorized state body.

The content of the application may include initiation of insolvency case and applying one of the procedures for restoring solvency or initiation of insolvency proceedings against the debtor and declaring it bankrupt, as well as for the commencement of liquidation proceedings. In all cases, an application for insolvency can be submitted to the court in written or electronic form. The state fee from applications submitted to the economic courts for the recognition of organizations and citizens as bankrupt is collected three times the amount of the basic calculated amount[3].

It is appropriate to separate the general and special requirements for the contents of the application for insolvency. Articles 149-151 of the Economic Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan determine the general requirements for the content of the application for insolvency. Specific requirements for the content of an insolvency petition are determined by who is submitting the petition.

The debtor's application to initiate insolvency proceedings against him shall be signed by:

- the head of the debtor legal entity;
- the debtor individual entrepreneur;
- the debtor individual or their representatives.

According to Article 39 of the Law "On Insolvency" of Ruz in the debtor's application for initiation of insolvency proceedings against them, the following must be indicated:

- name of the court to which the application is submitted;
- name of the applicant (surname, name, patronymic) and their location (postal address), electronic mail (upon availability);
- amount of creditors' claims for monetary obligations recognized by the debtor;
- amount of the debtor's arrear for compensation for harm to the life or health of employees, labor payment and severance benefits payable to the employees of the debtor;
- amount of remuneration payable under copyright agreements;
- amount of debt on taxes and fees;
- substantiation of the inability to satisfy creditors' claims in full;
- information about claims against the debtor accepted for proceedings by the courts, as well as about executive documents presented for indisputable (non-acceptance) write-off;

- information about the debtor's property, including monetary funds, receivables;
- numbers of bank accounts of the debtor, postal address of the bank;
- list of attached documents.

The application of the debtor-individual entrepreneur about their insolvency shall also contain information about the obligations of the debtor not related to entrepreneurial activity.

Originals or certified copies of the following documents must be attached to the debtor's application for insolvency proceedings against them:

- documents confirming the existence of debt, as well as the inability of the debtor to satisfy the claims of creditors in full, other circumstances that were the ground for the application of the debtor;
- constituent documents of the debtor – a legal entity, documents on state registration of a legal entity or an individual entrepreneur, as well as a copy of the passport of a natural person;
- list of creditors and debtors of the debtor with a breakdown of accounts payable and receivables and an indication of the location (postal address), e-mail address (upon availability) of creditors and debtors of the debtor;
- balance sheet or documents replacing it of the debtor – legal entity as of the last reporting date;
- documents on the composition and value of the property of the debtor, who is a natural person or an individual entrepreneur;
- decision of the founders (participants) or the owner of the property of the debtor – a legal entity with respect to the debtor's application to the court to initiate insolvency proceedings against them;
- minutes of the meeting of the debtor's employees at which a representative of the debtor's employees was elected to participate in the consideration of the insolvency case, if such a meeting was held prior to filing an application for initiating an insolvency case.

The debtor shall be obliged to send a copy of the debtor's application to creditors and other persons participating in the insolvency case. If prior to the submission of the debtor's application, a representative of the founders (participants) or the owner of the debtor's property, a representative of the debtor's employees are elected (appointed), then a copy of the debtor's application shall be also sent to these persons.

According to Article 39 of the Law “On Insolvency” of RUz the application of a creditor – a legal entity shall be signed by its head or representative, and the

application of a creditor – a natural person or an individual entrepreneur – by this natural person or their representative.

The creditor's application to initiate insolvency proceedings against the debtor must contain:

- name of the court to which the application is submitted;
- name (surname, name, patronymic) of the applicant and their location (postal address), e-mail address (upon availability);
- name (surname, name, patronymic) of the debtor and location (postal address), email address (upon availability);
- amount of the debtor's monetary obligation to the creditor from which the claim arose, as well as the term for its execution;
- evidence of the validity of the creditor's claims, including a court decision that has entered into legal force, evidence confirming the recognition of these claims by the debtor, a notary's executive inscription;
- list of attached documents.

The creditor shall be obliged to send a copy of their application to the debtor.

To the creditor's application to initiate insolvency proceedings against the debtor shall be accompanied documents confirming the debtor's monetary obligations to the creditor, as well as the existence and amount of debt. In case of insolvency in a simplified procedure and insolvency of a natural person, evidence of payment of expenses for the payment of remuneration to the judicial manager shall be accompanied.

In addition, the following documents, if any, shall be attached to the creditor's application for insolvency proceedings against the debtor:

- creditor representative's a power of attorney confirming the authority to sign the application;
- decision of the court that considered the creditor's claims against the debtor;
- writ of execution (writ of execution, payment claims accepted by the debtor, writ of execution by a notary, etc.) or evidence confirming the recognition by the debtor of the creditor's claims.

The application of the authorized state body to the court to initiate a case on the insolvency of an enterprise, in the charter fund (authorized capital) of which there is a state share and (or) debt to the Republic of Uzbekistan for monetary obligations shall be submitted to the court in compliance with the requirements provided for creditor's application and accompanying documents (Articles 41 and 43 of Law “On Insolvency” RUz). The State Asset Management Agency is an

authorized state body. In addition, the State Tax Service can apply as an authorized state body. The application of the state tax authorities and other authorized body on initiation of insolvency proceedings against the debtor must be accompanied by evidence of the adoption of measures to pay debt on taxes and fees in accordance with the legislation.

Based on the above, instead of the conclusion, the following specific procedural aspects of formalization an application for initiation of insolvency proceedings can be noted:

firstly, an application for inability to pay can be submitted by the debtor, creditor and authorized state body.

secondly, insolvency proceedings may be initiated by the court only if there are temporary or permanent signs of insolvency.

thirdly, on the basis of substantive and procedural legislation, general and special requirements for the content of an insolvency application are established.

fourthly, the state fee from applications submitted to the economic courts for the recognition of organizations and citizens as bankrupt is collected three times the amount of the basic calculated amount.

fifthly, failure to comply with the requirements for the form and content of the application for insolvency will result in the court refuse to accept the application for proceedings or return the application.

References:

1. Economic Procedural Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan // National Database of Legislation, 01/25/2018, No. 02/18/EPC/0623.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 12, 2020 No. LRU-763 "On Insolvency" // National Database of Legislation, April 13, 2022, No. 03/22/763/0306.
3. The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On State Duty" January 6, 2020 No. LRU-600 <https://lex.uz/docs/5528070>

